

more than one $d-d$ transition, indicating distortion from octahedral symmetry^{4,6}.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. R. D. Patel and Dr. Raman P. Patel for their kind interest in the work. Our thanks are also due to Mr. D. H. Desai for IR spectra.

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Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Aspartic Acid Chelates of Pr(III) and Gd(III) Ions

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Manuscript received 17 October 1973; revised 8 April 1974;
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THE complexes of aspartic acid with metal ions like Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} have been reported in literature by many workers^{1,2}. Batyaev *et al.*³ have reported the stability constants of complexes of aspartic acid with La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} and Nd^{3+} at 25°. Trivedi and Sunar⁴ have reported thermodynamic functions of aspartic acid chelates of Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} recently. The present work is intended to study the stabilities of complexes of aspartic acid

with Pr^{3+} and Gd^{3+} ions at different temperatures and determine overall changes in free energy, enthalpy and entropy. In this paper the stability constant of Pr^{3+} as given by Batyaev *et al.* is verified with the addition of the thermodynamic functions.

Experimental

Pr and Gd oxides were dissolved in the calculated amount of perchloric acid. The metal content of the solutions were gravimatically estimated, by precipitating as oxalate and then igniting as oxide. Other solutions were prepared in conductivity water. NaClO_4 was used to adjust the ionic strength. All the chemicals used were of A.R. (B.D.H. or equivalent) quality.

The constant temperature water was circulated through the titration vessel made of pyrex glass, from thermostat, where the temperature was controlled within 0.1°. The experimental procedure involved a series of pH titrations of aspartic acid with standard NaOH solution in the absence of and in presence of metal ions at different temperatures 35°, 45° and 55°. The sets for different pH titrations were made according to author's another paper under communication⁵. In all the titrations the volume (25 ml) and ionic strength (0.1M NaClO_4) were kept constant.

Curve A : Only for aspartic acid for both the experiments.
Curves B, C, D : For aspartic acid and Pr(III) at 35°, 45° and 55°.
Curves B', C', D' : For aspartic acid and Gd(III) at 35°, 45° and 55°.

Results and Discussions

The pH value of the systems B, C, D and B', C', D' is lower than the corresponding value in A indicating the liberation of proton due to complex formation.

The liberated proton has been calculated from the figure, which represents potentiometric titrations of aspartic acid with standard alkali in the absence and presence of metal ions at three different temperatures. No precipitation, was observed until pH of

		TABLE		
		35°	45°	55°
Pr(III)	log K_1	5.639	5.632	—
	log K_2	—	5.802	5.698
Gd(III)	log K_1	5.643	—	—
	log K_2	5.747	5.664	5.668

4.5 has been attained. At any pH between 3.0 to 4.5 the horizontal distances between the curves (obtained by titration of ligand directly and with metal corresponding to different temperatures) has been used to determine the additional base consumed or ligand complexed. From this value, $\bar{n}$ has been calculated. Formation curves for the metal ligand system were plotted using $\bar{n}$ and $-\log(\text{Asp})$ values. The stability constants were read directly from these formation curves at $\bar{n}$ values of 0.5 and 1.5 respectively. Calvin and Melchoir⁶ extension of Bjerrum's⁷ method was used for calculation. The results are given in the table.

Thermodynamic functions :

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) of complexes formed have determined at 35° and were found to be -7.921 Kcal./mole, -46.87 Kcal./mole and -126.5 Kcal./deg./mole for Pr(III) aspartate and -7.927 Kcal./mole, -52.10 Kcal./mole and -143.4 Kcal./deg./mole for Gd(III) aspartate respectively.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Department of Atomic Energy for financial assistance, Shri V. B. Sardesai, Principal, Bipin Bihari College, Jhansi for encouragement, Prof. S. R. Solauki, Principal and Dr. H. P. Agarwal, Head of the Chemistry Department, M.A. College of Technology, Bhopal for providing facilities to carry out this work and to Dr. G. Viswanath for necessary help and guidance.

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Studies in Copper(II) Chelates. Part VIII. Action of Ethylenediamine and Trimethylenediamine on some Copper(II) Chelates of Tridentate dibasic Schiff Bases

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Manuscript received 6 November 1973; revised 22 April 1974;
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WE describe here the results of our attempted synthesis of copper(II) mixed chelates of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{SB})]$ (or $[\text{Cu}(\text{tn})(\text{SB})]$) (en = ethylenediamine; tn = trimethylenediamine; SBH_2 = tridentate dibasic schiff base e.g. glycine-salicylaldehyde, glycine-hydroxynaphthaldehyde etc.) by the action of en(or tn) on $[\text{Cu}(\text{SB})_2]$ or by the action of SBH_2 on $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})\text{aq}]$ (or $[\text{Cu}(\text{tn})\text{aq}]$). These reactions lead to N,N'-ethylene (or N,N'-trimethylene) bis(salicylaldiminato) copper (II)

Experimental

Procedure A :

Copper acetate (·001 mole) was taken in ethanol (20 ml) and to this was added a solution of the Schiff base^{1,2} (·001 mole in 30 ml hot ethanol). The mixture was refluxed for about 30 mins. A green, olive green or a yellow compound separated. Ethylenediamine or trimethylenediamine (·001 mole) was added and the mixture refluxed for 3-4 hrs. Products were purified, analysed for metal and nitrogen and examined microscopically and spectrophotometrically.

Procedure B :

The tridentate Schiff base^{1,2} (·001 mole in 30 ml ethanol) was added to the deep violet solution of copper acetate (·001 mole in 20 ml ethanol) and ethylenediamine (·001 mole) or trimethylenediamine, and the products treated as above.

Results and Discussion

Procedure A and procedure B constitute two straight forward routes to our projected goal. The reactions may lead to (1) mixed chelates ($[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{SB})]$) formation; (2) ethylene of trimethylenebridged complexes, $[(\text{SB})\text{Cu}(\text{en})\text{Cu}(\text{SB})]$; or to (3) amine exchange. Analytical data given in Table 1 convince us that amine exchange occurs and we get copper(II) complexes of the quad adentate Schiff base of the amine and the appropriate hydroxyaldehyde as shown in (A) and (B).

Amine exchange reactions have been observed with bidentate mono basic Schiff base complexes of copper(II)^{3,4}, nickel(II)⁵, and also with quadridentate Schiff base complexes of copper(II)³. To our knowledge this is for the first time that an amine exchange reaction on a tridentate Schiff base complex is reported to yield a complex of a quadridentate Schiff base. The ease of the amine exchange, expectedly, depends on the substituent group (X) on